

IODINE CONTENT IN SOME NIGERIAN FOODS

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ABSTRACT.

Iodine aids thyroid hormone. Its deficiency causes goiter, poor growth in infancy, infertility and other forms of iodine deficiency disorders. Considering the importance of iodine in the development of human being, it is important to source for foods of reasonable iodine content. To this end, iodine value of some selected Nigerian foods has been determined using standard method to know the extent of their possible contributions to iodine intake. Foods values on a dry weight basis (μkg^{-1}) were: fish group (155-144); legume group (2.54-15.23); meat group (123); cereal group (5.08-16.49); root and tuber group (6.35-10-15); vegetable and spices group (5.08-82.74) and fruits and masticatories group (2.54-27.92). The foods were calculated to provide between 1.7 and 69 μg of RDA. In areas, where cassava and cassava products are the main sources of food, this could lead to increased serum thiocyanate, a lower iodine intake, and hence goiter.

KEY WORDS: Iodine, Nigerian foods, goiter, treatment.

INTR ODUCTION

Inorganic minerals in foods are essential for life and are normally classified as ash (Anon, 2006a). These elements can be categorized into major and trace elements, with the latter being present at low levels in body tissues.

Iodine, which is the precursor of iodinated thyroid hormone, is very important in metabolism. The role of iodine in nutrition arises from the importance of thyroid hormones in the growth and development of humans and animals (Anon, 2006b). Thyroid hormones are synthesized in the thyroid gland by iodination and coupling of two molecules of the amino acid tyrosine in a process that is dependent on the adequate supply of iodine (Roti and Uberti, 2001). Iodine deficiency causes cretinism in children (Feldt-Rasmussen, 2001) and only a trace amount is requires in whole life of humans. Thyroxine increases the rate of chemical reactions in the body by improving the activity (Delange, 2000). Iodine deficiency may reduce the production of thyroxine thus the thyroid gland enlarges resulting in goiter. Goiter is associated with the consumption of goitrogens. Large amounts of these substances are found in cauliflower, cassava, as well as other plants and even waterborne sources. Goitrogens inhibit iodide metabolism by the thyroid gland and in turn inhibit thyroid hormone synthesis. However, goitrogens are not an important cause of goiter in developed countries, since they are destroyed by cooking and the foods they are found in do not often play an important role in the customary diets. They are however, linked to the goiter in less developed parts of the world, especially to where cassava is a dietary staple (Wardlaw, 1999).

Extensive epidemiological studies have shown that endemic goiter in man and animals are related to iodine deficiency. Information from UNICEF indicates that 20% of the Nigerian population is iodine deficient (Anon, 1990). The WHO estimates that 20million people in the world have varying degrees of preventable brain damage due to the effects of iodide deficiency on fetal brain development (Hetzal, 1994). The aim of this work is to determine levels of iodine in some edible biological food materials to provide data that might be of interest in extending knowledge on nutritional quality of the food samples and to determine the extent of their possible contributions to iodine intake.

Table 1: Iodine content in fish group (μgkg^{-1})

Samples	Mean \pm SEM
Catfish	144.15 \pm 10.38
Tilapia (<i>Tilapia nicotilus</i>)	138.07 \pm 10.50
Crayfish(<i>Procambaris clarkii</i>)	177.61 \pm 10.41
Stockfish	155.01 \pm 10.41

Table 2. Iodine content in legume group (μgkg^{-1})

Samples	Mean \pm SEM
Brown Beans (<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>)	15.23 \pm 0.23
White beans (<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>)	15.23 \pm 0.24
Groundnut (<i>Arachis hypogea</i>)	2.54 \pm 0.16
Melon (<i>Citrullus lunatus</i>)	10.46 \pm 0.15
Soya beans (<i>Glycine max</i>)	13.96 \pm 0.23
African locust beans (<i>Parkii biglobosa</i>)	3.81 \pm 0.01

Table 3. Iodine content in meat group (μgkg^{-1})

Samples	Mean \pm SEM
Meat (beef) cow	1236.09 \pm 10.50

Table 4. Iodine content in cereal group (μgkg^{-1})

Samples	Means \pm SEM
Rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i>)	5.08 \pm 0.21
Yellow maize (<i>Zea mays</i>)	16.49 \pm 2.25
Guinea corn (<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>)	7.61 \pm 0.08
Bread	23.81 \pm 1.25

Table 5. Iodine content in root and tuber crops group (μgkg^{-1})

Samples	Mean \pm SEM
Cassava tuber(<i>Manihot esculenta</i>)	6.35 \pm 0.22
White yam (<i>Discorea rotundata</i>)	10.15 \pm 0.10
Yellow yam (<i>Discorea cayanensis</i>)	6.35 \pm 0.10
White gari (<i>Manihot esculenta</i>)	5.25 \pm 0.20

Table 6: Iodine content in vegetable crops, spices and fibers group (μgkg^{-1})

Samples	Mean \pm SEM
Green leaf (<i>Amaranthus spp</i>)	66.72 \pm 0.51
Water leaf (<i>Talinium triangulae</i>)	75.28 \pm 0.56
Pumpkin leaf (<i>Cucubita spp</i>)	82.74 \pm 0.45
Onion (<i>Allium cepa</i>)	5.08 \pm 0.21
Sugar nut (<i>Irvingia gabonensis</i>)	12.69 \pm 0.41
Cherry pepper (<i>Piper annum</i>)	11.42 \pm 0.45

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The food items samples for this work were obtained from a local market in Akure, Ondo state, Nigeria in March, 2002. The samples include: *Vigna unguiculata*, *Arachis hypogea*, *Citrullus lunatus*, *Glycine max*, *Parkia biglobosa*, *Oryza sativa*, *Zea mays*, *Manihot esculenta*, *Discorea rotundata*, *Discorea cayanensis*, *Amaranthus spp*, *Talinium triangulare*, *Cucubita spp*, *Allium cepa*, *Irvingia gabonensis*, *Piper annum*, *Musa parasidiaca*, *Carica papaya*, *Cola nitida*, *Cola acuminata*, *Elaeisis guinesis*, *Tilapia nicotilus*, *Procambaris clarkii*, *Sorghum bicolor*, bread, cow meat, walnut, stockfish, catfish.

Table 7. Iodine content in fruits and masticatories group (μgkg^{-1})

Samples	Means \pm SEM
Ripe fresh plantain (<i>Musa parasidiaca</i>)	2.54 \pm 0.01
Ripe pawpaw (<i>Carica papaya</i>)	10.15 \pm 0.01
Unripe pawpaw (<i>Carica papaya</i>)	2.54 \pm 0.01
Kolanut (white) (<i>Cola nitida</i>)	13.96 \pm 0.50
Kolanut (red) (<i>Cola acuminata</i>)	12.08 \pm 0.80
Walnut	3.81 \pm 0.45
Palm kernel seed (<i>Elaeis guinensis</i>)	27.92 \pm 0.50

The samples were washed in distilled water, oven dried at 105^oC, ground, sieved (2mm) and kept in airtight containers prior to analysis. The samples (0.5g) were dry-ashed in a furnace at 550^oC for 2h. The ashed samples were dissolved in a litter quantity of distilled water, filtered and made up to 100cm³ with distilled water. The iodine liberated from the digestion process was then titrated against freshly prepared 0.001M solution of sodium thiosulphate using 2 drops of 1 percent starch solution as indicator. The iodine content of each sample was then estimated from the volume of the titrant used (Asaolu and Asaolu, 1999).

Statistical analysis: All analysis was in triplicate. Mean values and SEM were presented.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The iodine content in all the foods analyzed is depicted in Tables 1-7. Iodine content was highest in the fish samples, though it was higher in vegetables, spices and fiber group (5.08-82.74 μgkg^{-1}) compared to all other groups. Roots and tubers were generally low in iodine content and ranged from (6.35-10.15 μgkg^{-1}). Cereal and fruits and masticatories groups contained intermediate iodine levels from 5.08-23.81 μgkg^{-1} and 2.54-27.92 μgkg^{-1} respectively. The results obtained from this study were in agreement with some food values of iodine in Britain (Wenlock *et al.*, 1982) and Nigeria (Akindahunsi *et al.*, 1993; Asaolu and Asaolu, 1999; Abulude, 2004). The RDA of iodine is 150 $\mu\text{g day}^{-1}$. If 100g of the dry Nigerian foods with the least iodine were consumed per day, one would have consumed 1.7 μg of iodine in a day, while the highest would provide 69 μg . The Institute of Medicine (2001) recommended a daily intake of 150 μg iodine, but considered intake of up to 1000 $\mu\text{g day}^{-1}$ safe for adults. Probably the minimum intake to prevent goiter is 50 $\mu\text{g day}^{-1}$. According to Akindahunsi *et al* (1993) in Western Germany, where there remains a lot of concern that the iodine intake might not be high enough to prevent goiter, the average intake is 80 $\mu\text{g day}^{-1}$ while British subjects ingest an average of 255 $\mu\text{g day}^{-1}$, infants, toddlers and teenagers in America have been estimated to ingest up to 395,368 and 955 $\mu\text{g day}^{-1}$ and these values seen to be on the increase (Wenlock *et al.*, 1982). However, other reports seen to indicate that iodine intake in the USA is now on the decrease. Swedish pensioners have been estimated to have average intake of 318 and 246 $\mu\text{g day}^{-1}$ for men and women respectively (Wenlock *et al.*, 1982). Presently, in Nigeria, major sources of iodine (milk, bread, meat and fish) are taken only occasionally because of cost considerations. Rice, cassava and cassava products are more consumed by the populace. Different processing methods of food preparation are attributed to nutrient loss in foods. This has affected iodine contents loss due to volatilization.

People in deficient areas can receive iodine as an additive to food for water or by direct administration. Direct administration of iodine is usually in form of iodized oil, but potassium iodide or iodine in Lugol's solution can also be given. Iodine is also usually added at a ratio of salt between 1:10,000 and 1:50,000 the level can be adjusted for the estimated daily consumption of salt, which varies from less than 3g a day to 15g per day (Anon, 2006b) Administration of iodized oil requires direct contact with

each target subject in contrast to iodized salt. Iodized oil has usually been administered via the primary health care system. Iodized oil provides adequate iodine for several years after its initial administration. Iodine had also been added to a number of foods, which include: bread, candy and vitamin tablets (Dunn and Dunn, 2001).

CONCLUSION

This work has revealed that sources of iodine were bread, meat, fish and vegetables. The iodine contents of all other basic foods were found to be low. It is very likely that prolonged intake of these foods may result in iodine deficiency goiter, but reports have shown that fortification of foods and water with iodine have been a successful measure in correcting those deficiency

REFERENCE

- Abulude F.O.2004. Determination of iodine in some Nigerian tropical grain plants. Bioscience Res.Comm.16 (1): 29-32.
- Anon.1990. Focus in nutrition. Daily Times, Monday, November 1, p28.
- Akindahunsi A.A, Adewusi S.R.A, Torimiro S.E.A, Oke O.L.1993. Food composition and endemic goiter in Akungba and Oke Agbe of south western Nigeria. Food Comp. And Analy.6: 156-167.
- Anon. 2006a.The world healthiest foods. Iodine. The George Mateljan Foundation.
- Anon. 2006b. Iodine. Section 1. Nutritional disorders and therapy. Chapter 4.Mineral deficiency and toxicity. The Merck manual of diagnosis and therapy.
- Asaolu S.S and Asaolu M.F.1999. Iodine distribution in some Nigerian leafy vegetables. J. Technoscience.3: 33-34.
- Delange F. 2000. The role of iodine in brain development. Proc Nutr Soc. 59(1):75-9.
- Dunn J.T, Dunn A.D. 2001.Update on intrathyroidal iodine metabolism. Thyroid.11 (5):407-14.
- Feldt-Rasmussen U. 2001. Iodine and cancer. Thyroid.11 (5): 483-6.
- Hetzel B.S.1994.Iodine deficiency and fetal brain damage. New England. J.Med.331: 1770.
- Institute of Medicine. 2001. Dietary Reference Intakes for Vitamin A, Vitamin K, Arsenic, Boron, Chromium, Copper, Iodine, Iron, Manganese, Molybdenum, Nickel, Silicon, Vanadium, and Zinc. National Academy Press: Washington DC,
- Roti E, Uberti ED. 2001. Iodine excess and hyperthyroidism. Thyroid. 11(5): 493-500.
- Ward law G.M.1999. Perspectives in Nutrition.4th ed. McGraw-Hill Companies. USA. Pp 524-526.
- Wenlock R.W, Buss D.H, Moxon R.E and Bunton N.G.1982. Trace nutrients. 4. Iodine in British Food. J. Nutr. 47:381-390.

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